

FISH UTILISATION OF BIOENGINEERED INTERTIDAL HABITATS IN THE THAMES ESTUARY

WANDA BODNAR¹, STEPHEN COLCLOUGH² AND AMY PRYOR¹

¹Thames Estuary Partnership, University College London, Room 117,
26 Bedford Way, London WC1H 0AP
w.bodnar@ucl.ac.uk

²Institute of Fisheries Management, PO Box 679, Hull HU5 9AX

Abstract

Over the past two centuries the floodplain of the Thames Estuary has been progressively encroached upon or reclaimed, leading to the depletion of intertidal habitats such as saltmarshes, seagrass beds and mudflats. This loss of intertidal habitats is believed to negatively impact fish populations, likely attributable to the declining availability of suitable nursery grounds. In response to this ongoing habitat loss, modern riverside developments along the Thames now incorporate setbacks from the estuary's edge to help facilitate the establishment of intertidal habitats, thereby improving the environment for fish and other wildlife.

Fauna surveys conducted from 2017 to 2023 revealed favourable results for these bioengineered intertidal habitats, affirming their effectiveness in serving as nursery areas especially for juvenile fish species such as Common Goby, European Seabass and the critically endangered European Eel.

The current scientific understanding of fish utilisation of these bioengineered intertidal habitats should actively guide the planning and creation of new sites and the potential modification of existing ones, especially considering the ongoing loss of intertidal habitats in the UK.

Keywords

Fish - Common Goby - European Seabass - European Eel - bioengineered - intertidal - habitat - Thames Estuary

Introduction

Estuaries and estuarine intertidal habitats rank among the world's most biologically productive ecosystems, serving as vital nursery areas for fish to spawn, feed and seek refuge (Vasconcelos *et al.* 2011). The accessibility of these nursery areas is crucial for sustaining commercial fish populations, as supported by substantial evidence (Nagelkerken *et al.* 2015). However, many of these intertidal habitats have been lost or become heavily engineered due to increasing urbanisation of major estuaries (Richardson & Soloviev 2021; ZSL 2021).

Previous page: Yellow Flag *Iris pseudacorus*. © London Essex & Hertfordshire Amphibian and Reptile Trust

A noteworthy case is the Thames Estuary where, over the past two centuries, the floodplain has been progressively encroached upon or reclaimed. This has resulted in the gradual loss of intertidal habitats such as saltmarshes, seagrass beds and mudflats (Green *et al.* 2021; ZSL 2021). Despite the well-documented recovery of the Thames Estuary since the 1960s, transforming it into a major nursery ground for ecologically and commercially important fish species, only about 1% of its banks retain a natural profile today (Colclough *et al.* 2005). This loss of natural habitat is believed to negatively impact fish populations, likely attributable to the declining availability of suitable nursery grounds (Maitland 2003; ZSL 2021).

Estuary Edges

In response to the ongoing loss of estuarine habitats, contemporary riverside developments along the Thames Estuary are set back from the estuary's edge, facilitating the creation of intertidal habitats to enhance the environment for fish and other wildlife (EA 2008). These bioengineered intertidal habitats collectively fall under the umbrella

Figure 1: Estuary Edge sites documented in the design guidance along the Thames Estuary. © Wanda Bodnar

of a planning guidance for developers called Estuary Edges, published in 2008, which is collaboratively managed by the Thames Estuary Partnership (TEP), Environment Agency (EA) and the Port of London Authority (PLA) (Figure 1) (Colclough & Cucknell 2018).

Estuary Edges exhibit a diverse range of flora and are categorised based on design principles, ranging from naturalised set backs to encroachments (Figure 2) (Estuary Edges 2023).

The primary role of these habitats is to soften the hard, built-up edges of the estuary, particularly along solid flood defences, while providing essential ecosystem services. These services include mitigating tidal flow energy and serving as crucial nursery grounds for fish,

Figure 2: Estuary Edge sites based on design principle. © www.estuaryedges.co.uk

facilitating their vertical and horizontal migrations throughout the estuary - a phenomenon known as selective tidal stream transport (STST) (Petrou 1999; Forward & Tankersley 2001).

Estuarine juvenile fish leverage STST, which is more energetically efficient than active swimming, by moving upstream or downstream with the tide's head and entering areas of reduced flow associated with soft marginal zones where they feed or await the next tidal cycle (Amoo-Gottfried 1998; Colclough *et al.* 2000; Colclough *et al.* 2002).

Since 2017, TEP has taken the lead in conducting annual fauna surveys of Estuary Edges, with a primary focus on demonstrating the utilisation of these sites by aquatic fauna, particularly juvenile fish.

Methodology

The fauna surveys were led by TEP with the help of Stephen Colclough, Fisheries Scientist and Chair of the Estuarine & Marine Specialist Section at the Institute of Fisheries Management (IFM), with support from the Environment Agency and the Port of London Authority.

Between 2017 and 2023 nine Estuary Edge sites were surveyed (Table 1 and Figure 1).

Fauna survey

A recognised best practice multi-method survey approach, which have been used on the Thames Estuary since 1994, was modified for Estuary Edges and employed throughout the surveys (Colclough *et al.* 2000; Colclough *et al.* 2002; Elliot 2002; Coates *et al.* 2007).

The survey equipment used were:

- 15m* 2.7m* 3mm knotless mesh seine net
- small mesh winged fyke net (50cm height; trap length 3m* mesh size reduces from 10, 8, 6.5mm, all knotless)

Where applicable, seine netting was conducted on the foreshore in front of the site during a rising tide, just before the tide covered it completely (Figure 3). This was

#	Site	Design principle	Date of construction	Survey method(s) & number of samples		Date of the survey(s)
				Fyke net	Seine net	
1	Barking Creek Set Back (western side)	Naturalised set back	2012	3 2 2 2	- - - -	17 October 2017 1 October 2019 10 August 2021 12 September 2023
2	Barking Creek at Barking Barrier (eastern side)	Naturalised set back	2006	4 3	- -	18 October 2017 31 August 2022
3	Battersea Reach Terracing	Vegetated intertidal terrace	2005	3 3	4 3	3 October 2017 17 July 2023
4	Deptford Creek (Saxon Wharf, Thanet Wharf, Vertical Wall Renewal)	Vegetated intertidal terrace	2009	2	3	19 October 2017
5	Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East	Vegetated intertidal terrace	1997	3 3	3 4	6 October 2017 13 October 2023
6	Point Wharf, Greenwich	Vegetated intertidal terrace	Early 2000s	4 3 3 - - 3 - 3	3 2 3 4 4 3 3	5 October 2017 1 July 2019 9 August 2021 3 August 2022 2 November 2022 21 July 2023 1 November 2023
7	Royal Wharf, Silvertown	Vegetated intertidal terrace	2014	4	-	4 October 2017
8	Wandsworth Riverside Quarter	Vegetated intertidal terrace	2008	4	3	2 October 2017
9	West India Dock <i>Phragmites</i> bed	Vegetated intertidal terrace	2000	4	-	20 October 2017

Note that in 2017 the three sites at Deptford Creek were sampled as one from the Deptford Creekside Centre.

Table 1: Survey sites, methods used and date of sampling

Figure 3: Seine netting at Battersea Reach Terracing. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 4: Fyke net deployed at Battersea Reach Terracing. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 5: Measuring of total fish length (in this case a Zander). © Wanda Bodnar

carried out considering earlier research that showed that juvenile fish follow the head of the tide, enabling them to access vegetated areas along the edges as quickly as possible (Amoo-Gottfried 1998; Colclough *et al.* 2000; Colclough *et al.* 2002).

The fyke nets were secured with small metal stakes and weights before the tide inundated the sites (Figure 4). The fyke nets were recovered on the falling tide just prior to the cod-end drying out.

Each fyke and seine net samples were separated into aerated buckets. All fauna captured were identified to species level and were counted. Additionally total length (L_T , mm) of the fish captured was also measured (Figure 5).

All fauna processed was returned to the water as soon as possible.

Fauna analysis

An overview is provided to summarise the total number of individuals (N), species (S) and the relative abundance (%) of fish species across all sites and years, followed by describing the changes observed over the years at those sites that were sampled more than once (Barking Creek at Barking Barrier (eastern side), Barking Creek Set Back (western side), Battersea Reach Terracing, Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East and Point Wharf, Greenwich) (Table 1).

Fish community analysis

Community ecology analysis was also conducted to find out: 1) if fish species composition increased in similarity between the sites and design principle over the years, and 2) length frequency distribution of the three most abundant species was compared between the sites for each year. In addition, to find out, 3) if fish are able to swim onto the vegetated intertidal terraces, abundance and diversity of the fyke and seine net samples were compared.

Fish species composition

To find out if fish species composition increased in similarity between the sites and design principle over the years, the relative abundance of each fish species was calculated for the entire sampling period. Bray-Curtis similarity was then calculated and ordinated using non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS) to investigate similarities in fish species composition. The results were submitted to analysis of similarities (ANOSIM) to test if there were statistically significant differences between fish species composition.

Length frequency

Length frequency of the three most abundant species was compared between the sites for each year using a Kruskal-Wallis test.

Vegetated intertidal terraces

To find out if fish were able to swim onto the vegetated intertidal terraces, within each year the mean relative abundance and mean Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H') of the seine and fyke net samples were compared between Battersea Reach Terracing and Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East using independent samples t -tests (Washington 1984).

Data analysis

All the statistical analyses were performed in R v4.3.3 and RStudio 2023.12.1 (R Core Team 2024) using `vegan` v2.6.4 (Oksanen *et al.* 2022) and visualised with the `ggplot2` v3.5.0 package.

Results

Fauna analysis

A total of 1,361 specimens were sampled belonging to 16 different species between 2017 and 2023 (Figure 6 and 7).

Site overview

Most of the sites now encompassing Estuary Edges were sampled in a first major study in 2017 (Colclough & Cucknell 2018). Five of these sites were then sampled again at varying intervals in the subsequent years (Table 1).

Barking Creek at Barking Barrier (eastern side)

A small new creek system was established on the east side of Barking Creek, just above the confluence with the Thames Estuary, in 2006. Brushwood bundles were staked into the creek sides to stabilise the new sloping clay banks. Further brushwood bundles were staked transversely across the bed of the new creek.

The initial assessment took place in July 2007 when a King's College MSc student (Gray 2007), assisted by Stephen Colclough and the Environment Agency, employed small winged fyke nets and a 15m micromesh seine net to sample the site. The findings revealed an abundance of fish, predominantly Common Goby *Pomatoschistus microps* (L) and juvenile European Seabass *Dicentrarchus labrax* (L). The creek operated according to expectations, displaying a distinct main channel and drainage channels during the

Figure 6: Total number of individuals. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 7: Species richness. © Wanda Bodnar

ebbing tide. Subsequently, in August 2012, another King's College MSc student (Yates 2012), supported by Stephen Colclough from the Institute of Fisheries Management, conducted further sampling. Then the *Phragmites* growth was so heavy that fish could not penetrate the site and no drainage channels were visible.

In 2017 the site looked the same initially. However, on close inspection there were small clear patches within the marsh. Drainage on the ebb was moving under the transverse timber bundles, forming the beginning of a true saltmarsh creek. In these channels large catches of Common Goby, European Seabass and Flounder *Platichthys*

flesus (L) were made.

During the 2022 survey it was once again observed that *Phragmites* growth had further proliferated extensively, covering the entire creek, rendering open water and drainage channels indiscernible. Nevertheless, fish species including Common Bream *Abramis brama* (L), Common Goby, Common Roach *Rutilus rutilus* (L), European Seabass and Flounder were identified at the periphery of the site.

Barking Creek Set Back (western side)

Established in 2011, this site also underwent sampling by a King's College MSc student (Yates 2012). While adhering to a similar overall design involving brushwood bundles and stakes, the lower half of the creek was lacking transverse structures. In 2012, the creek maintained an open water channel throughout all tidal stages. Various fish species, including young European Seabass, Common Goby and even juvenile Common Dace *Leuciscus leuciscus* (L) were captured along the entire length of the newly formed creek. Yates (2012) recommended against implementing transverse structures in creek development to preserve an open water channel for fish movements.

By 2017, sampling indicated a complete *Phragmites* cover in the upper reaches of the creek, while a deep incised channel persisted in the lower section. Fyke nets placed in the middle and lower parts of the creek consistently captured Common Goby, European Eel *Anguilla anguilla* (L), European Seabass and Flounder in 2017, 2019, 2021, and 2023.

This extended dataset stands out due to its longevity, effectively illustrating the evolutionary changes of both of these sites (Barking Creek at Barking Barrier (eastern side), Barking Creek Set Back (western side)) and their impact on fish utilisation over time. It further substantiates Yates's 2012 observations (echoed in Colclough & Cucknell 2018) that the placement of transverse structures across the creek should be avoided for optimal fish utilisation, emphasising the importance of unrestricted drainage.

Battersea Reach Terracing

Constructed in 2005, this site featured gabion basket structures with implanted vegetation. A protective boom at the site's forefront aimed to prevent floating debris from encroaching onto the area.

The initial survey in 2017 revealed significant erosion, with rock material washing out from the gabion basket structures. From the foreshore, several juvenile Common Goby, Common Roach and European Seabass were captured. On the terrace, two European Seabass and three European Eels were captured in fykes. Concerns arose about the boom's impact, as its 1 metre skirt beneath the main structure could impede fish immigration during the rising tide and block emigration during the falling tide, potentially causing strandings.

Due to limited space, the 2017 capture of European Eels suggested active feeding across the site's top near the seawall at high tide. It was speculated that these eels might be permanent residents on the terrace, seeking refuge in the gabion baskets' spaces during low tide around the vegetated stands.

By 2023, the boom was found partially derelict, failing to move with the tide for half its length. A single European Eel was captured on the terrace, reinforcing the notion of active feeding during high water and residing in the gabion spaces. The vegetation,

now more extensive, had grown. The seine netting in front of the terrace yielded low numbers of Common Bream, Common Dace, Common Goby, Common Roach, European Seabass, Flounder, Three-spined Stickleback *Gasterosteus aculeatus* (L) and a Zander *Sander lucioperca* (L).

Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East

Installed in 1997 as part of the Greenwich Millennium Exhibition 2000, these terraces marked the pioneering introduction of experimental intertidal set back terrace structures in the UK. Configured as a series of stepped levels, the terraces incorporated some *Phragmites* planting. By 1998, pioneer stands of saltmarsh plants, like Sea Aster *Aster tripolium*, had established themselves, showcasing the potential for natural colonisation if the terraces were appropriately positioned at the right tidal height with suitable substrates, provided a local seed bank existed, possibly in Bow Creek at the time.

In 1998, the first fish surveys on the terraces were conducted by King's College MSc student (Amoo-Gottfried 1998), supervised by Stephen Colclough. These surveys captured a mix of freshwater species, such as juvenile Common Dace and more expected estuarine species like Common Goby, Flounder, Sand Smelt *Atherina presbyter* (C) and European Smelt *Osmerus eperlanus* (L) on multiple occasions. A subsequent survey by the Environment Agency in 2003 yielded similar results. Notably, Flounder and Common Goby captured in both studies were only found on the foreshore in front of the terrace and occasionally on the first step if it connected with the shoreline. These benthic species seemed reluctant to ascend the vertical face of the structure during the flooding tide, possibly due to the lack of a swim bladder in the case of Flounder.

In 2017 and again in 2023, sampling at the extreme downstream end of the terrace structure revealed the evolution of a drainage channel close to the foreshore access point. This channel, adjacent to the ends of gabion structures used in terrace construction, provided a sinuous gradient for fish immigration and emigration. In both years, juvenile Common Goby, high number of European Eels, European Seabass and Flounder were found on the foreshore and on the terraces, particularly near this drainage feature.

Over the years, most terraces on the front developed dense monocultures of *Phragmites*, while the extreme downstream end exhibited more variability with a mix of different saltmarsh plants, including Sea Aster.

Point Wharf, Greenwich

The four terrace structures installed at Point Wharf in the early 2000s, situated alongside a slipway, serve as an excellent site for instructional surveys for student groups. Consequently, Point Wharf was subject to sampling in 2017, 2019, 2021, 2022, and 2023. Seine netting in front of the structure yielded extensive fish data, including Common Bream, Common Dace, Common Roach, European Seabass, European Eel, Flounder, Sand Smelt, Thin-lipped Grey Mullet *Chelon ramada* (R) and even a Short-snouted Seahorse *Hippocampus hippocampus* (L) over the years. However, due to the challenging access to the terraces, which requires a ladder down the sea wall, fyke nets were only utilised on the terraces themselves in 2017 and 2023, capturing predominantly European Eels and European Seabass. It is postulated that these fish reside among the debris and eroded base of the structure, similar to the conditions observed at Battersea

Reach Terracing. Over time, stands of *Phragmites*, Sea Aster and other plants have become more established.

A notable concern pertains to the front of the terrace structures, where the front edge forms a continuous wall of sheet piling standing up to 1 metre above the riverbed. As erosion or washout occurs at the front of the terraces and pools of water, up to 40cm deep, persist behind the steel sheet piling as the tide drops. Unfortunately, this water drains out through the terrace as the tide recedes further, leading to occasional findings of small numbers of deceased juvenile Common Dace, European Seabass, Flounder and even juvenile Zander in these dry pools at low tide. To mitigate fish mortality without compromising terrace stability, reducing the height of the sheet piling to decrease pool depth and incorporating v-notches to facilitate drainage during the ebb is suggested. In certain areas, material movements across the terrace are diminishing the vertical drop at the terrace front to nearly zero, presenting a practical option where feasible.

Fish community analysis

A total of 1,334 individual specimens were collected belonging to 13 different species between 2017 and 2023 (Figure 8).

Throughout the entire sampling period, euryhaline species, such as Common Goby (45.1%) and European Seabass (41.9%), were the most abundant fish species followed by the European Eel (3.4%).

Figure 8: Relative abundance of fish species. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 9: Non-metric multidimensional scaling (MDS) ordination plot comparing fish species composition. © Wanda Bodnar

Fish species composition

Comparison of fish species composition showed that there was no significant difference between sites (ANOSIM, $R = 0.164$, $p = 0.13$) and years (ANOSIM, $R = -0.1689$, $p = 0.88$), however, there was a significant difference between design principle (ANOSIM, $R = 0.2179$, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 9).

Length frequency

With the exception of 2022 (Chi square = 2.78, $df = 1$, $p = 0.09$), there was a significant difference in length distribution of Common Goby between sites in all other years (2017: Chi square = 19.74, $df = 4$, $p < 0.05$; 2019: Chi square = 21.12, $df = 1$, $p < 0.05$; 2023: Chi square = 21.11, $df = 2$, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 10).

Similarly, with the exception of 2021 (Chi square = 1.8, $df = 1$, $p = 0.17$), there was a significant difference in length distribution of European Seabass between sites in all other years (2017: Chi square = 14.53, $df = 4$, $p < 0.05$; 2022: Chi square = 3.88, $df = 1$, $p < 0.05$; 2023: Chi square = 72.29, $df = 3$, $p < 0.05$) (Figure 11).

There was no significant difference in length distribution of European Eel between sites in 2017 (Chi square = 4.62, $df = 3$, $p = 0.2$) and 2023 (Chi square = 1.8, $df = 1$, $p = 0.17$) (Figure 12).

Vegetated intertidal terraces

There was no significant difference observed between the mean relative abundance of fyke and seine net samples in 2017 at Battersea Reach Terracing (independent samples t -test, $df = 3$, $t = 0.657$, $p = 0.55$) and Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East

(independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 8, *t* = -2.3968e-16, *p* = 1), and in 2023 at Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 4, *t* = 0, *p* = 1). However, there was a significant difference observed at Battersea Reach Terracing in 2023 (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 7, *t* = 4.92, *p* < 0.05) (Figure 13).

Similarly, there was no significant difference observed between the mean Shannon-Wiener diversity index (*H'*) of fyke and seine net samples in 2017 at Battersea Reach Terracing (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 2, *t* = -1, *p* = 0.42) and Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 2, *t* = -0.98576, *p* = 0.42), and in 2023 at Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 5, *t* = 2.1228, *p* = 0.08). However, there was a significant difference observed at Battersea Reach Terracing in 2023 (independent samples *t*-test, *df* = 2, *t* = -4.8734, *p* < 0.05) (Figure 14).

Opposite above: **Figure 10:** Length frequencies of Common Goby, shaded area indicates 0-year group size. © Wanda Bodnar

Opposite below: **Figure 11:** Length frequencies of European Seabass, shaded area indicates 0-year group size. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 12: Length frequencies of European Eel, shaded area indicates an average 0-year group size. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 13: Mean relative abundance. Error bars represent standard errors

Figure 14: Mean Shannon-Wiener diversity index (H'). Error bars represent standard errors. © Wanda Bodnar

Discussion

The fish species composition exhibited a notable significance solely based on design principles. However, it is important to highlight that the two sites classified as naturalised set backs, namely Barking Creek Set Back (western side) and Barking Creek at Barking Barrier (eastern side), are situated within the same creek. Consequently, additional research is needed at a different location, yet with a comparable design (e.g. Syon Park meadows in West London), to enable more conclusive findings.

The predominant species, Common Goby and European Seabass, were notably

associated with naturalised set backs, with high abundance of juveniles present suggesting these sites serve effectively as nursery areas. Visual observations hinted at the potential transformation of the two Barking Creek sites into a saltmarsh habitat, evident from the significant growth of *Phragmites* beds and some well-developed drainage channels. Saltmarshes are known to be preferred predation refuges and feeding grounds for European Seabass, with the Thames Estuary acting as one of the largest European Seabass nurseries in the southern North Sea (Kirk *et al.* 2002). Similarly, the benthic Common Goby is one of the dominant species found in saltmarshes and managed realignments (Lafaille *et al.* 2000; Colclough *et al.* 2005; Nunn *et al.* 2016). This observed evolution of the two sites may explain the elevated number of individuals found.

The European Eel, ranking as the third most abundant species, demonstrated a close association with vegetated intertidal terraces, particularly thriving at Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East in 2023. Here, the presence of a drainage channel facilitated fish entry into the site, potentially explaining the heightened number of Flounder also caught in fyke nets. This marks a notable evolution from earlier surveys where only a few Flounder were documented on the terraces (Colclough *et al.* 2005).

Comparing fyke and seine net samples at Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East and Battersea Reach Terracing revealed differences in mean abundance and diversity in 2023, with only one European Eel captured at Battersea Reach Terracing. This discrepancy likely stems from design issues at Battersea Reach Terracing, characterised by the protective boom intended to prevent litter from entering the site (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Protective boom at Battersea Reach Terracing during high tide. © Wanda Bodnar

Figure 16: Pool and dry areas with some fish stranding observed at Point Wharf, Greenwich. © Wanda Bodnar

The behaviour of this boom may impede fish movements across the boundary, hindering their migration onto the upper intertidal habitat during the tidal cycle. This interference may diminish the site utilisation, in contrast to the more accommodating conditions at Greenwich Millennium Terraces - North East (see 'Site overview' section).

Limitations

It is necessary to acknowledge the limitations of these findings. Notably, not all sites underwent annual sampling and extensive sampling was predominantly conducted in 2017 and 2023. Moreover, variations were observed across seasons during the sampling process and in the number of samples collected across sites.

Regarding the data collected, the scope was confined to abundance sampling and length measurements, lacking consistent recording of environmental parameters.

Recommendations

Based on these survey results, the following recommendations should be considered:

1. Under the Biodiversity Net Gain scheme site improvements for better fish access should be made at Battersea Reach Terracing (Figure 15) and at Point Wharf, Greenwich (Figure 16).
2. To maintain a robust and inclusive dataset, continue the annual sampling across as many sites as possible, encompassing all design principles, including the new sites created by Thames Tideway Tunnel (e.g. Chelsea and Albert Embankment Foreshore).
3. Ensure consistent collection of environmental data (temperature, dissolved oxygen and salinity) throughout the entire sampling process to provide a comprehensive context for the observed trends and to allow correlation analysis.
4. In addition to annual sampling, explore the benefits of incorporating sampling over the seasonal and diel cycle to capture the nuanced variations in fish utilisation at the sites over different time scales.
5. Consider a long-term study by partnering with an academic institution to:

- a. Incorporate true saltmarsh habitats for comparison to better understand fish utilisation across the design principles.
- b. Assess the viability of incorporating environmental DNA (eDNA) sampling as a complementary approach to traditional methods for identifying potentially overlooked fish species and perform a comparative analysis between findings obtained through eDNA sampling and those derived from traditional methods.
- c. Investigate feeding rates and dietary patterns by refining survey methodologies (e.g. measuring and comparing biomass of fish that enter and exit the site) and systematically collecting and analysing fish stomach content.

Conclusion

In summary, these results underscore the significance of bioengineered intertidal habitats for juvenile fish within the Thames Estuary, particularly considering the substantial presence of Common Goby, European Seabass and the critically endangered European Eel. The current state of scientific knowledge regarding fish utilisation of these sites should actively inform the design of new locations (e.g. implementing unrestricted drainage) and the possible modification of existing sites (e.g. incorporating v-notches at vertical wall frontage), especially considering the substantial loss of intertidal habitats in the UK in recent decades. Moving forward, annual sampling across as many sites as possible should be considered with the integration of new sites and methodologies, and the collection of additional data.

References

- AMOO-GOTTFRIED, K. 1998. *Fish utilisation of enhanced intertidal habitat in the Tidal Thames*. MSc Thesis. King's College, London.
- COATES, S., WAUGH, A., ANWAR, A. & ROBSON, M. 2007. Efficacy of a multi-metric fish index as an analysis tool for the transitional fish component of the Water Framework Directive. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **55**(1): 225-240.
- COLCLOUGH, S.R., DUTTON, D., COUSINS, T. & MARTIN, A. 2000. *A Fish Population Survey of the Tidal Thames*. Environment Agency, Bristol.
- COLCLOUGH, S.R., GRAY, G., BARK, A. & KNIGHTS, B. 2002. Fish and fisheries of the tidal Thames: management of the modern resource, research aims and future pressures. *Journal of Fish Biology* **61**(sA): 64-73.
- COLCLOUGH, S.R., FONSECA, L., ASTLEY, T., THOMAS, K. & WATTS, W. 2005. Fish utilisation of managed realignments. *Fisheries Management and Ecology* **12**: 351-360.
- COLCLOUGH, S. & CUCKNELL, A. 2018. *Fish Survey Programme Report 2018*. Estuary Edges.
- ELLIOTT, M. 2002. Fishes in Estuaries. pp. 410-509. Blackwell Science Ltd., Oxford.
- ENVIRONMENT AGENCY. 2008. *Estuary Edges: Ecological Design Advice*. Report.
- ESTUARY EDGES. 2023. *Estuary Edges Case Studies*. <https://www.estuaryedges.co.uk/case-studies/> (accessed: 30/10/2023).
- FORWARD, R.B. & TANKERSLEY, R.A. 2001. Selective tidal-stream transport of marine animals. In: *Oceanography and Marine Biology*. An annual review. **39**: 305-255.
- GRAY, J. 2007. Fish utilisation of restored intertidal habitats in a tidal backwater of the Thames estuary. MSc Thesis. King's College London.

- GREEN, A.E., UNSWORTH, R.K.F., CHADWICK M.A. & JONES, P.J.S. 2021. Historical Analysis Exposes Catastrophic Seagrass Loss for the United Kingdom. *Frontiers in Plant Science* 12.
- KIRK, R.S., COLCLOUGH, S. & SHERIDAN, S. 2002. Fish diversity in the River Thames. *Lond. Nat.* 81: 75-81.
- LAFFAILLE, E., FEUNTEUN, E. & LEFEUVRE, J.C. 2000. Composition of fish communities in a European macrotidal salt marsh (the Mont Saint-Michel Bay, France). *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 51(4): 429-438.
- MAITLAND, P.S. 2003. *The status of smelt Osmerus eperlanus in England*. English Nature Research Report 516.
- NAGELKERKEN, I., SHEAVES, M., BAKER, R. & CONNOLLY, R.M. 2015. The seascape nursery: a novel spatial approach to identify and manage nurseries for coastal marine fauna. *Fish and Fisheries* 16: 362-371.
- NUNN, A.D., CLIFTON-DEY, D. & COWX, I.G. 2016. Managed realignment for habitat compensation: Use of a new intertidal habitat by fishes. *Ecological Engineering* 87: 71-79.
- OKSANEN, J., BLANCHET, F.G., FRIENDLY, M., KINDT, R., LEGENDRE, P., MCGLINN, D., MINCHIN, P.R., O'HARA, R.B., SIMPSON, G.L., SOLYMOS, P., STEVENS, M.H.H., SZOECIS, E. & WAGNER, H. 2022. vegan: Community Ecology Package. R package version 2.5-2. Cran R.
- PETROU, A. 1999. *Investigations into the utilisation of tidal transport by juvenile fish on their upstream migration in the Tidal Thames*. MSc placement report. Environment Agency, Crossness.
- RICHARDSON, M. & SOLOVIEV, M. 2021. The Urban River Syndrome: Achieving Sustainability Against a Backdrop of Accelerating Change. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*: 18(12): 6406.
- VASCONCELOS, R.P., REIS-SANTOS, P., COSTA, M.J. & CABRAL, H.N. 2011. Connectivity between estuaries and marine environment: Integrating metrics to assess estuarine nursery function. *Ecological Indicators* 11: 1123-1133.
- WASHINGTON, H.G. 1984. Diversity, biotic and similarity indices: a review with special relevance to aquatic ecosystems. *Water Research* 18: 653-694.
- YATES, J. 2012. *The Change in Fish Abundance and Diversity over time in Man-made Intertidal Habitats on the Thames Estuary*. Unpublished MSc Dissertation, King's College, London.
- ZSL. 2021. *The State of the Thames 2021: Environmental trends of the Tidal Thames*. MCCORMICK, H., COX, T., PECORELLI, J. & DEBNEY, A.J. (Eds).. ZSL, Regent's Park, London.